

REPORT ON CURRENT INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS SOLUTIONS IN EUROPE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of this report is to give an overview of existing Industrial Symbiosis solutions in Europe in terms of approaches, with a more local character: platforms, facilitating the circular economy and methodologies, promoted and funded by European institutions that foster IS at EU level.

Data has been collected from different sources such as scientific publications, databases, statistics, previous EU funded projects, ECoP, etc.

Data are contextualised into the European framework, paying particular attention to the legislation such EU Directives: EU Waste Framework Directive, Circular Economy Package, REACH and Industrial Strategy among others.

In addition, the main barriers have been identified to understand the problems of implementation and permanence of IS solutions to overcome in the SYMBA project.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CA – Consortium Agreement

CE - Circular Economy

D – Deliverable

DoA – Description of Action

EC – European Commission

ECHA - European Chemicals Agency

ECoP - European Community of Practice

EIP - Eco-industrial Park

GA – General Assembly

H2020 – Horizon 2020 The 8th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

HEU – Horizon Europe – the 9th framework Programme of the EC for research, technological development and innovation activities.

IPR – Intellectual Property Right

IS - Industrial Symbiosis

NISP - National Industrial Symbiosis Programme

PC – Project Coordinator

REACH - Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals

REAL - Rapid Evidence Assessment of Literature

SC – Steering Committee

SME – Small and Medium Enterprise

TEVA - Total Economic Value Added

WP – Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

The definition of industrial symbiosis (IS) in working terminology is the transactions involving material, energy and water as the core of network exchanges (Domenech and Davies, 2011). In many cases, these transactions not just involve physical resources but also involve knowledge transfer and expertise. This resource transfer may stimulate collaboration in other areas, resources and expertise, reducing transaction cost and identifying new opportunities.

The concept around circular economy (CE) has been gaining weight in European legislations, until becoming one of the core tools in order to achieve a more sustainable future. The main concept of CE is to change the current perspective of linear production and consumption into a more circular system. IS has been identified as a potential solution for enhancing environmental solutions while still achieving economic benefits, which is the idea behind CE. IS is a systems approach to a more sustainable and integrated industrial system, which identifies business opportunities that leverage underutilised resources (such as materials, energy or water) (Lombardi & Laybourn, 2012).

The 2018 Amendment to the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/CE) established IS as “the use by one company or sector of underutilised resources broadly defined (including waste, by-products, residues, energy, water, logistics, capacity, expertise, equipment and materials) from another, with the result of keeping resources in productive use for longer”.

Consequently, the purpose of this deliverable is the mapping of IS solutions in order to create a clear description of the situation of IS solutions across Europe and gathering the main barriers which hinder the implementation of IS solutions. This deliverable contributes to WP3, Task 3.1 titled “Data collection on Industrial Symbiosis solutions”.

It is essential to know the set of IS solutions and how they are organised in platforms, approaches and methodologies around Europe in order to understand the IS ecosystem, serving as support and basis for next steps in the SYMBA project.

1.1 ABOUT THE PROJECT

IS solutions are one of the most important approaches to fostering the circular economy, promoting the use of waste as resources, and avoiding environmental pollution. IS solutions aim to keep resources improving the value chain, to shift towards a more sustainable and integrated industrial ecosystem, and to discover new business opportunities from undervalued resources such as energy, materials, water, assets, expertise, etc. This approach is based on the 4R hierarchy (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Recover) but it goes further than waste management. IS solutions can promote a closed-loop system that optimises the resources, reduces the production of waste and enhances the economic and environmental goals.

SYMBA aims to create a new and innovative Industrial Symbiosis methodology that will be useful across the European Union, adapted to regional and local bio-based ecosystems. The SYMBA project will develop an accessible and user-friendly AI database, recommending local and regional IS innovative solutions, helping to build circular and sustainable value chains. The project is aligned with the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and its approach is based on the

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creation and validation of innovative IS methodology for the bio-based sector, starting from existing expertise and knowledge collected from SYMBA consortium partners. Individuation of criteria to select regional hubs, and the creation of IA databases including waste relation matrix, monitoring tools, cooperation and networking with local networks across the EU. SYMBA's cutting-edge approach will enhance the way towards a sustainable and circular economy, transforming the bio-based solutions, while reducing the depletion of natural resources such as water, soil and GHG emissions. The bio-based industrial sectors involved in the project are packaging, agri-food, wastewater, textile and waste valorisation. The implementation of ground-breaking digital tools, such as AI solutions, will develop an environment for the sustainable industrial networks for the next decades by using an accessible and user-friendly database promoting local innovative operations and IS solutions in the bio-based value chains.

1.2 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The goal of this current deliverable is the compilation of IS solutions across Europe regarding IS in terms of state of the play, gaps, value chains, societal and legal barriers, stakeholders, etc. The mapping of IS solutions has been developed from different sources:

- Legislation implemented at European, national and regional level.
- Active or past projects, programs or initiatives that implement industrial symbiosis solutions.
- Databases and statistical reports.
- Scientific peer-reviewed reports.

The mapping is conducted through a Rapid Evidence Assessment of Literature (REAL), as it provides a structured and rigorous research of the topic in question. This method was selected in opposition to the Systematic Review (SR) which is a much more in-depth method. However, given the time constraints, the REAL method is more suitable for this report as it makes concessions regarding the depth of the search. Systematic reviews are generally resource intensive and time consuming. However, both methodologies follow the same structure to deliver an evidence-based report.

The general scope of the report is at three levels: European, national and local, as cases can be found at all levels, and they will be used in the mapping. The IS solutions mapping is based on the use of secondary raw materials with recycled content, reduction of consumption of virgin materials, residual heat and renewable energy, carbon capture and GHG emissions, waste and wastewater streams. Hence, the gathering of information is set to find the main resources such as energy, plastics, water, metals, biological materials, and the different emissions to air, soil and water (GHG, wastewater and waste) in order to find opportunities of the bio-based value chains such as agri-food, textile, plastics and packaging, wastewater and water in the framework of IS solutions.

The IS solutions have been classified in accordance with their nature (i) in platforms, which can serve as an exchange media of resources between companies and can be used as a market to exchange different by-products flows; (ii) in methodologies based on funded European projects, they are organised plans with more managed networks with a third part as a coordinator, and (iii) in approaches which are spontaneous and self-organised structures of IS solutions, habitually initiated due to the necessity of the industries to achieve the

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reduction of energy and resource consumption The current policies and strategies for IS solutions in Europe have been identified in order to understand the legal and political framework where IS solutions are developed. Furthermore, the main barriers (technical, economic, societal, informative, cultural, etc.) to overcome in the implementation of IS solutions have been identified.

Figure 1 : Scheme for Industrial Symbiosis.

Relation with other Tasks and Deliverables

The deliverable provides an overall overview of the mapping of IS solutions across Europe in order to understand the current situation. Hence, the outcomes of this deliverable are the support and contextualise the comprehension of the general situation of the different IS solutions, categorised in platforms, approaches and methodologies. Therefore, it is directly related to T3.3 Internal co-creation and weighing. The data obtained in D3.1 will be the basis of the internal co-creation approach to be followed to weigh the criteria considering the methodology, and T3.3. Evaluation of industrial symbiosis prioritised solutions, as well as to the activities developed in the framework of WP5 and WP6. The created database will be uploaded on the project website (WP8). Thus, the results of T3.1 will be the groundwork of T5.4. Policy roadmap for SYMBA's contribution to the enhancement of European industrial sustainability, and task T6.1 will be built on the results of the mapping of IS solutions.

1.3 POLICIES AND STRATEGIES FOR IS SOLUTIONS IN EUROPE

Circular economy programs have been gaining strength in the last decades, because they play a crucial role to achieve the Paris Agreement. IS solutions are also involved in these goals, as it is part of the circular economy programs, as the CE strategy "Closing the loop An

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action Plan for the Circular Economy (European Commission, 2015)” that mentions the role of IS solutions as a concrete measure to transform “waste or by-products of one industry to become inputs for another”. The IS solutions in Europe exist both as self-organised activity, being the direct cooperation between industrial stakeholders based on trust, geographical proximity and equity; and facilitated activity, managed by a coordination entity facilitating the expertise and information among industrial organisms.

Regarding policies and strategies that foster Industrial Symbiosis at European level, the main EU policies and strategies are The European Green Deal, A New Circular Economy Action Plan, EU Waste Framework Directive, REACH, Industrial Strategy and Resource Efficient Europe Flagship Initiative:

The European Green Deal is a strategy that protects and promotes the IS solutions within the EU. It aims to enhance the EU in a modern, prosperous society with a zero waste and competitive economy, avoiding the emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where the growth of the economy does not depend on the consumption of raw materials. (European Commission, 2019).

A New Circular Economy Action Plan will enhance the economy of Europe and will promote the vision of opportunities to implant the circular economy in all sectors, focusing on the development of circular markets and products, business models and services. The conversion of consuming patterns has to transform the concept of the waste to a new raw material (European Commission, 2020c). IS solutions play a crucial role in the 2020 Circular Economy Action Plan, where it is displayed as a means of transforming production systems and therefore a way of achieving circularity in the industrial sector.

The **Waste Framework Directive** (2008/98/CE) established the concept of industrial symbiosis; as it is the main legislation at European level that fosters and promotes the potential role of IS solutions. The Waste Framework Directive encourages the implementation of IS solutions where possible: “In order to promote sustainable use of resources and industrial symbiosis, Member States should take appropriate measures to facilitate the recognition as a by-product a substance or an object resulting from a production process the primary aim of which is not the production of that substance or object if the harmonised conditions established at Union level are respected. The Commission should be empowered to adopt implementing acts in order to establish detailed criteria on the application of the by-product status, prioritising replicable practices of industrial symbiosis”. (European Commission 2018a).

REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals) is a regulatory framework to harmonise the chemical processes in the EU and provides procedures for assessing and collecting information on the properties and hazards of chemical substances. All the companies have to register their substances and they need to work together with other companies who are registering the same compound. ECHA evaluates individual registrations for their compliance and the Member States of EU evaluate selected substances to clarify possible concerns for human health or for the environment. Their scientific committees assess if the risks of substances can be managed. (ECHA, 2020).

The European Commission brought the **New Industrial Strategy** for Europe to light in 2020. This policy is based on how the companies can address the transition to a greener, more digital and more circular economy, while standing competitive in a global market.

Paying special attention to the industrial ecosystems and their stakeholders. (European Commission, 2020b).

The **Resource Efficient Europe Flagship Initiative** is another European legislation that is focused on fostering IS solutions under the Europe 2020 Strategy. The initiative mentions IS as the means to improve the re-use of raw materials, which is a milestone in the Flagship Initiative. (European Environment Agency, 2020).

However, there are data gaps in the assessment of the IS solutions and there exists a lack of harmonised frameworks for evaluating IS solutions and assessing the IS activities. Most of the time, there is a lack of monitoring of IS activity over time. (European Commission, 2018).

1.4 MAPPING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS IN EUROPE

Several mappings of IS solutions have been conducted by several authors, from general gathering of IS solutions in Europe (Domenech et al., 2019), a mapping of IS solutions in the Northern countries (Johnsen et al., 2015), to a report regarding all existing eco-industrial parks (EIP) (Massard et al., 2014). EIP are defined as “a community of manufacturing and service businesses seeking enhanced environmental and economic performance through collaboration in managing environmental and resource issues including energy, water, and materials” (Massard et al., 2014). EIP can also be described as eco-innovation parks or eco-parks.

Despite the assessments for IS solutions are not always completed or available across other projects, the reported input of IS collaboration creates interesting economical, environmental and social benefits and foster the circular economy, minimising the production of waste and reducing dependence on raw materials and energy. However, transaction cost and low commercial margins are the barriers to be overcome in the future (Domenech et al., 2019).

1.5 CATEGORIZATION OF IS SOLUTIONS

Industrial Symbiosis networks can be characterised by their geographical scope and organisational structure; however, according to Domenech et al (2019) they can be further characterised into three types:

1. Self-organised networks, when there’s direct interaction among the industrial actors. They generally are organised at national or local level, being involved with governments or municipalities.
2. Managed networks, where there is generally a third party that organises and is involved in coordinating the activities. They tend to have a more top-down approach than self-organised networks.

The managed networks classification can be further divided into two types:

- Facilitated projects generally have a bigger geographical scope than self-organised networks, either a national or European approach. Furthermore, they tend to be linked to a project or funding system (Life+, Horizon or Interreg)

- Planned networks also present European or national approaches; however in these cases, the projects are generally organised by a third party that dictates the synergies and action plan and is generally not directly related to the project.
3. There are some digital platforms (Krom et al., 2022), which serve many companies for exchange waste streams., knowledge and energy and operate as product-service systems.

The SYMBA project has taken the previous categories described above, and has developed three new categories based on them in order to harmonise the nature of different IS solution typologies. As a result, three categories have been created: Platforms, approaches and methodologies (Figure 2).

Figure 2 . Classification and categorizations of IS solutions

- **Platforms:** According to Krom et al. (2022), "Digital platforms have recently been recognised as a means to facilitate a circular economy: they can serve as a market for excess capacity; can be used to operate product-service systems, thereby facilitating maintenance and repair activities; and can empower people to share knowledge and co-create products and services for a circular economy". Digital platforms can help in finding possible synergies and the cooperation between companies by supporting the transaction of updated information and enhancing the exchange of materials and energy. (Benedict et al., 2018) The digitalisation of the companies can improve different aspects that enhance IS solutions such as

monitoring the availability, the location of resources and quality and energy streams of the processes. (Antikainen et al., 2018).

- **Approaches:** It is directly related to self-organised networks, as they tend to have a more local approach, being self-organised by the industries in the industrial parks itself. This classification gathers active projects or case studies that implement IS. They are generally initiated out of necessity by the involved industries and stakeholders; with the support of both private and public funding. Commonly, it consists of a cluster of complementary industries that cooperate with each other to reduce resources and energy. There is some level of organisation and coordination among the stakeholders. Companies provide feedback and create an ecosystem. (Chertow, 2000).
- **Methodologies:** They tend to have a more European approach as most of them are funded by European institutions that create a plan or scheme of possible IS solutions in order to implement them in specific regions. This classification aligns more with managed networks, as it generally involves a third party that coordinates and organises the network and that itself isn't a part of the industries. The methodologies cluster respond to a top-down approach, as it is generally an external stakeholder who develops the original plan or idea to implement IS. They can be active in different regions within different countries, in contraposition to approaches, which tend to only affect one specific area.

2. RESULTS OF THE MAPPING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS SOLUTIONS IN EUROPE

The mapping of IS solutions has demonstrated the existence of a large number of IS solutions and case studies with different scopes and characteristics. The following chapter showcases the situation in Europe regarding IS implementation and the most typical characteristics for each depicted category (i.e., platforms, approaches, methodologies). It should be noted that given the large number of existing solutions, only the most remarkable have been mentioned in this chapter. The Annexes provide all the information collected from the IS mapping. In addition, a dataset with the mapping was built and openly available throughout the Zenodo open repository, being available [here](#).

As mentioned previously, the mapping will be focusing mainly on five value chains: i) wastewater, ii) waste, iii) plastic and packaging, iv) textile and v) agri-food, as they are related to the industrial partners' expertise. The involved sectors for each project are shown in the Annexes.

The gathering of IS solutions in Europe has showcased the existence of certain factors that are determinant for each category such as the location, size of the network, complexity or even related to the involved industries.

A large number of the self-organised networks found are located in northern countries, mainly Finland, Sweden, Norway and Denmark; even though there are also cases in countries like Italy and Germany. This is related to higher restrictions regarding waste management and in general, a harsh climate that promotes industries to be located in certain areas and close together (Domenech et al., 2019).

Large hotspots of high-density industrial facilities were discovered in certain areas of Europe, being found mainly in 5 areas: Western Germany, Northern Italy, Northern France, Belgium and Netherlands. A recent hotspot was found near Valencia (Spain).

Smaller hotspots can be found in the bigger European cities across the map (Scaler, 2020b). In each country, there are other specific and more local hotspots, where industrial symbiosis is more implemented. In the case of Spain, the regions of Valencia and Barcelona have a multitude of small projects fostering industrial symbiosis, therefore not all will be gathered due to its small size.

The variation in geographical scope of Industrial Symbiosis solutions depends mainly on the value chains that are involved. There are a certain number of factors that are more typical for European projects, or on the contrary, some resource values can only be found in local industrial parks. This is gathered in previous mappings that have been conducted of Industrial Symbiosis solutions in Europe (Johnsen et al., 2015; Domenech et al., 2019).

Figure 3 . Overview of the IS solutions in Europe derived from the mapping.

2.1. PLATFORMS

Digital platforms are online tools that serve as a bridge between companies from different sectors, which help to establish synergies, exchange resources or even share technical information. Several types of platforms are gathered within this category, from websites ecoindustria which are focused on fostering the reuse of resources at local level, to national and European funded projects with an extensive network involving several countries.

Firstly, local and regional platforms are the most typical case. These platforms are digital databases that connect different industries located in the same area with the aim of reducing waste and resources. Examples of this first level are:

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- **Ecoindustria**¹ is an example of a IS local solution, located in Barcelona. It helps to find potential synergies between local companies through an online platform.
- **SIMVAL**², a regional platform promoted by the Agencia Valenciana de Innovación (AVI), which aims to implement industrial symbiosis in the Valencia region (Spain).
- **SIMBYLAY**³ is a similar regional IS platform, also in the Valencia region, led by AIDIMME, Instituto Tecnológico Metalmeccánico, Mueble, Madera, Embalaje y afines.

The main objective of this project is to support industries to implement IS solutions.

The second level of platforms are the national platforms, which are promoted by the governmental agencies in the region or receive European funding. The main difference between the previous typology is the scope, as the second type is not restricted to an area but is a rather complex network at national scale. Some examples of national level platforms are:

- **BeCircle**⁴ is a national platform in Germany that aims to promote the development of a closed-loop ecosystem. It is a platform which supports IS solutions helping developers and managers, such as network operators and industrial actors, as well as finding solutions to establish sustainable synergies that improve environmental strategies to achieve the circular economy.
- **Floow2**⁵ (Netherlands), this national IS platform is a digital marketplace that helps to link the demands and supplies between companies from different sectors. The platform facilitates useful information regarding excess in resources or machinery to possible shortages.
- **eSymbiosis**⁶ (Greece): Development of knowledge-based web services to promote and advance Industrial Symbiosis in Europe.
- **Symbiosis platform**⁷ (Italy). This platform is a website where industries from different areas and sectors can share their own wastes such as energy, materials or different resources so other industries can utilise them.

Finally, the third level of platforms are the international platforms, which foster IS solutions, prioritising, planning and managing eco-industrial park initiatives in a holistic perspective. Examples of international platforms are the following:

- **SHAREBOX**⁸ is a good example of an international IS solutions platform. It is a platform that provides a logical workflow which implements possible synergies between companies and organisations, optimising information in real-time in order to share resources such as energy, residues, water or another waste stream in an optimised close system.
- **UNIDO**⁹ tools present the best example of an international platform, as they have been implemented by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization

¹ Ecoindustria (2018)

² SIMVAL (2018)

³ SIMBYLAY (n.d.)

⁴ Climate-KIC (n.d.)

⁵ FLOOW2 (n.d.)

⁶ LIFE 3.0 - LIFE Project Public Page. (n.d.)

⁷ Symbiosis Platform (2020)

⁸ SHAREBOX – seamless sharing. (n.d.)

⁹ UNIDO Knowledge Hub. | Eco-Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)

(UNIDO). Five different tools were created in order to assess all IS solutions in Europe. Thus, a general mapping is created to facilitate implementation of IS in other regions. The EIP Selection Tool helps to analyse different EIP in several countries. This helps to classify all of the existing projects. The EIP Assessment Tool analyses all the previously mentioned EIP against the International Framework for Eco-Industrial Parks. This tool aims to organise and prioritise the initiatives. The EIP Policy Support Tool has the goal to assist other entities with technical support in order to support policy makers. The EIP Opportunities Monitoring Tool's main objective is to report the reuse of resources from the EIP implemented case studies.

Regarding platforms, many solutions have been initiated, however a big number of them are not active or the website itself has never been implemented. This is mainly due to the complexity of maintaining a network and creating new synergies, without constant support from involved actors, or specific technical support that can find possible synergies that would otherwise not have been established (ENEA, 2015). SYMBA will contribute to its methodology to support the transformation from a linear to a circular economy due to assessing symbiosis in bio-based industrial ecosystems, the implementation of innovative digital tools, AI, and improving existing methodologies, overcoming the possible and future barriers and enhancing the IS solutions so that they can last over time.

2.2. APPROACHES

As mentioned previously, the approaches classification tends to have a more self-organised, local approach. Hence, the most IS solutions found in this category are EIP. Most of the EIP can be found in northern countries, as southern countries EIP are more recent, while northern countries have been implementing EIP for a longer period (European Commission, 2018).

A good example of an EIP is the Kalundborg case, which was the first IS solution implemented in Europe in 1960 (European Public Administration, 2016). This project is based on an EIP in Kalundborg, Denmark, which started to implement synergies between different companies. It started as a "self-organised" network, involving a large set of industries and sectors (i.e., from municipal services and facilities to agri food, chemical, and energy companies). As can be seen in Figure 4, many different types of synergies were established, from the exchange of sulphur, residual biomasses and sidestreams, water and wastewater, up to energy and fuels.

Figure 4 . Material Flows in the Kalundborg Industrial Ecosystem. Source: Kalundborg case study (UNEP, 2014)

In the same line, there are a few cases of EIP parks that implement IS solutions within different companies in Sweden such as Händelo¹⁰, a network of companies based on resource efficiency and agrifood sector as bioethanol production, and Landskrona, being the first example of an official IS solution in Sweden (started in 2003), it is formed by more than twenty companies of different sectors such as chemical, automotive or steelworks (Mirata et al., 2005). This is especially representative in the north, where all industries tend to be close together, enabling the establishment of exchanges and synergies. In the same line, Wolf and Petersson (2007) found that more than one third of companies in the forest sector in Sweden present IS, even if they are not classified as such, due to these interactions between companies that arise naturally.

Likewise, it should also be remarked that other networks such as Harjavalta (Massard et al., 2014), which is based on the optimization of iron production waste since World War II and Kemi-Tornio, a regional IS solution of different sectors such as forest industry, steel and mining companies and research and educational organisations, both of them located in Finland. The Styria Project, which is formed in a manufacturing cluster in Austria, implements synergies already for many years. The involved activities vary from agriculture to textile or energy production. They are good examples of self-organised networks driven by private partners but with the support of local governments (Hongmei et al., 2013).

There are numerous EIP that have implemented industrial symbiosis at some level. As detailed by Massard et al. (2014), some countries have a considerable number of EIP, having similarities in common. For instance, Belgium presents several types of EIP, where implemented synergies vary from energy exchanges to collective energy use and waste management through the implementation of photovoltaic or wind turbines. Examples of the

¹⁰ Händelo (n.d.)

latter EIP are Galaxia, Ecopark Hartberg, Kaiserbaracke Industrial Park and SMIGIN (see Annex 2 for more details).

In order to have an overall view of approaches implemented across Europe, some examples of EIP and their description are listed:

- **ULTIMATE¹¹ project** is an example of a funded IS solution fostered by the EU with a local character:
 - Increasing the capacity to recover water at an industrial complex. Tarragona, Spain.
 - Water reuse and heat recovery for horticulture.
 - Water reuse and material recovery in the chemical industry. Rosiano, Italy.
 - Mobile wastewater treatment unit. Nafplio, Italy.
 - Water recycling in the beverage industry. Lleida, Spain and Ostrava, Czech Republic.
 - Karmiel and Shafdan (The case study is located outside the EU but is funded by an EU institution).
 - Heat and resource recovery in chemical incineration plants. Saint-Maurice-l'Exil, France.
- **Kemi-Tornio¹²**, Sweden and Finland. This region implemented a mapping of the by-product flows, which was developed in 2013 and 2014.
The industries in the area, which belong to the processing industry, make important attempts to reduce their waste production and increase resource efficiency by developing new products from by-products and wastes. Some of the involved industries in the Kemi-Torni region include forest industry, steel, educational organisations and mining industry.
- **Ecopark Hartberg¹³**, Austria. The ecopark was first implemented in 1997 by the Hartberg Municipality. The whole ecopark relies on biogas, photovoltaic and wind turbines for the general electricity, heating and cooling needed by the industries. Furthermore, the waste and wastewater are also integrated in the approach, in order to reduce its impact. They still continue to establish synergies between the different industries.
- **SMIGIN¹⁴- Sustainable Management by Interactive Governance and Industrial Networking**, Belgium. Its main goal is to help EIP collectively manage environmental issues such as waste management, raw materials and energy, and wastewater. This initiative aims to identify sustainable and economic solutions for the companies that collaborate with each other.
- **Harjavalta EIP¹⁵**, Finland. Harjavalta is a small town in Finland, where synergies such as product efficiency, using roasting residues and waste oxides are applied to carbon

¹¹ ULTIMATE Water.(n.d.)

¹² Nordregio (2016 April)

¹³ Saikku, L. (2006)

¹⁴ Saikku, L. (2006)

¹⁵ Massard et al., (2014)

steelmaking and other related industries and have been implemented since World War II. The mining sector is the primary industry in the region.

- **Deux Synthe Industrial Park, France (2001)**¹⁶. Based on an old French association called Ecopal (Economie et écologie partenaires dans l'action Locale), it is helping to implement IS solutions. The network is formed by more than 17 companies which collaborate in the exchange of resources to foster the circular economy in the region.
- **ECOMARK**¹⁷ is a European funded project (2007-2013). Its main goal was to raise awareness on environmental topics in industrial areas, mainly Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), all without putting its economic or business development in risk.

The bio-based industry approaches are a key factor in the circular economy. The exploitation of bio-based waste streams such as wastewater, dedicated industrial crops, agro-industrial or food by-products to reuse as new resources and energy can close the loop. The replacement of fossil-intensive products can save up to 2.5 billion tons of CO₂ equivalent per year by 2030. The bio-based IS approaches foster the transition towards zero pollution, which is in line with the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2024). Many of the previously mentioned approaches have a close relation to biobased industries, either they are an active stakeholder, or they participate in some way in the synergies. However, specific bio-based approaches are:

- **Händelö**¹⁸, Finland (2006). Händelö Eco Industrial Park is a group of companies sharing resources. This approach is based on an incineration plant, agro-ethanol, grain based-ethanol production plant. The production of bioethanol generated by-products with high content of proteins to feed animals and CO₂, sent to the carbonic acid factory in Händelö.
- **Härnösand**¹⁹, Sweden (2022): the approach is within the Swedish food strategy and it is an extraordinary challenge that improves systemic innovation. It is focused on by-products for local food production. There is a local network for shared material flows making the food system more sustainable and resilient, using the IS solution practices.
- **AgriMAX**²⁰, Belgium (2016). It is a project based on extraction of significant amounts of different valuable materials from agricultural waste using flexible processing technologies such as filtration, thermal and enzymatic treatments, and solvent extraction. The approach will disclose the holistic potential of different agro-value chains using by-products and residues of potato, tomato, cereals and olives. These materials can be valorized to reach over 40% of high value use of the waste.
- **BASAJAUN**²¹, Various countries (2019). The BASAJAUN project is focused on maximising the wood and forest value through the use in wood construction. The by-

¹⁶ Massard et al., (2014)

¹⁷ CORDIS (2011, August 29)

¹⁸ Massard et al., (2014)

¹⁹ Massard et al., (2014)

²⁰ CORDIS. (2023b, June 28)

²¹ CORDIS. (2024, February 27)

products of wood such as fibres, veneers, bark, etc. are used as thermal insulation, composites, varnishes, systems as floors, roof, facades, etc.

More cases of EIP can be found in the Annex 2.

2.3. METHODOLOGIES

Regarding the methodologies category, as mentioned previously, they are aligned with facilitated and planned networks, which typically have a third person that coordinates and manages the solution top-down approach.

For this specific category, a good example is the deployment and promotion of the National Industrial Symbiosis Program (NISP). In this sense, the first NISP was first introduced in the United Kingdom by International Synergies Limited in 2003. It is used as an example of implementing IS solutions at a national scale, as it has been proven to stimulate economic growth, by creating jobs and supporting businesses to make a shift to a more sustainable environment (ENEA, 2015). It is the first network that has tracked the changes since implementing the synergies. It has been shown that it has generated from €1.7 billion to €2.9 billion of TEVA (Total Economic Value Added) for the United Kingdom economy (ENEA, 2015).

The assessment of the externally verified NISP outputs in the UK was carried out during the period between 2005 and 2013, including cost savings (€257M), additional sales (€251M), water saved (15Mt) and diverted from landfill (9Mt), hazardous waste eliminated (420 kt), virgin material saved (12 Mt), among others (ENEA, 2015).

Certain factors have been identified as crucial for a successful implementation of Industrial Symbiosis programmes, such as having an extensive network of industries, a group of experts that can spot opportunities and a specific data management system that benefits the given network. In addition, it has been proven to be beneficial to have expert facilitators that can connect the synergies from resources and waste from industries into other resources for different industries; and for that it is also necessary to have a unified data collection, as well as close contact with regulatory authorities and technical experts that can assess the synergies. As mentioned above, NISP has been implemented in many other countries such as Spain, with the SYMSITES²² project that implements regional IS solutions, fostering the technologies for waste management, wastewater treatment, sustainable energy production among others; or Ireland, with the ISS (Industrial Symbiosis Service) being the world's longest running facilitated industrial symbiosis programme in the world.

Additionally, there is a cross-cutting IS solution tool called SYNERGie^{®23} used by programs such as, for example, ISS (Northern Ireland) and FIIS (Finland), which hosts information over resources and organisations, providing background information of evidence-based solutions. It is used by many industrial stakeholders and sectors in order to find resource exchanges, cost savings and improve environmental sustainability.

Some IS programs based on the NISP methodology mentioned previously are:

²² CORDIS (2022, July 28).

²³ CORDIS. (2022d, October 6)

- **ISS²⁴**: Industrial Symbiosis Service (Northern Ireland, 2007- ongoing). It is based on the NISP model, and its main goal is to facilitate IS through connecting and supporting Northern Ireland companies. Since 2007 it has achieved a real economic benefit of around £40M through free advisory support, providing instructions and advice on taking advantage of waste resources for Northern Ireland companies. Landfill diversion, cost savings and job creation are some of the benefits that companies can obtain through the implementation of IS solutions. Invest NI (the regional business development agency which is part of the Department for the Economy of Northern Ireland) is a free service that helps more than 1600 companies across Northern Ireland. This IS solution program, since its beginning, has diverted more than 390,000 tonnes of waste to landfill.
- **PSNI- Programme National de Synergies Inter-Entreprises²⁵** (2015-2017): It is a program focused on resource efficiency based on technical, technological and tool training support to implement the IS solutions. PSNI applied NISP methodology through workshops in order to gain direct contact with companies. More than 130 synergies have been implemented. The legislative barriers are the most important hindrance found for the industrial symbiosis implementation.
- **FIIS- Finish Industrial Symbiosis²⁶**: Finland, 2013. The idea behind the FIIS program is to establish synergies that would otherwise not have been implemented. The main tools are business activation, exchange of information and the identification of possible synergies. All of the gathered information is located in a common SYNERGie[®] database, which allows users to monitor the different synergies and overcome benefits.

Furthermore, there are many IS solutions which are not necessarily inspired by the NISP model, that offer different methodologies and visions to achieve IS solutions across Europe in order to implement the transition towards a circular economy. Some examples of these solutions are:

- **SCALER²⁷** (Scaling European Resources with Industrial Symbiosis). Aims to increase the implementation of IS solutions by developing mechanisms to leverage resources, intensifying the IS initiatives and promoting cross-sectoral collaboration. SCALER uses different approaches to identify value chances, enhancing the business relationships in order to cooperate with each other. Creation of spaces of interaction, cooperation and engagement for the main stakeholders and foster the exchange of knowledge and materials in order to find the transition to a more sustainable economy.
- **TRIS²⁸** (Transition Regions towards Industrial Symbiosis) is a building block of circular economy, and its mission is to enable the competitiveness of the stakeholders

²⁴ Invest Northern Ireland. (n.d.)

²⁵ Institut National de l'Économie Circulaire. (2017)

²⁶ Interreg Europe - Sharing solutions for better policy. (n.d.)

²⁷ Scaler. (2020a)

²⁸ TRIS. (n.d.)

involved in IS solutions by supporting policy makers, identifying barriers and fostering structural local networks.

- **REDOL²⁹** (Aragon's REgional Hub for circularity: Demonstration of Local industrial-urban symbiosis initiatives) is a local project about the upgrading of management technologies, sorting and classification of waste streams, enhancing the solutions to used materials avoiding landfill and applying digital tools to improve value chains and interaction among stakeholders.
- **FISSAC³⁰** (Fostering industrial symbiosis for a sustainable resource intensive industry across the extended construction value chain) is based on the construction of IS models towards a zero-waste approach in the resource intensive industries (aluminium, steel, stone, chemical, etc) in order to find an harmonised technological framework to promote a close-loop economy.

The innovation on bio-based products and processes within the framework of the circular economy brings social and economic benefits such as creation of new jobs, new opportunities in coastal and rural areas, where the biological feedstock production happens. The bio-based IS methodologies are focused on high-value applications, resource efficiency, biomass exploitation, and digital technologies for managing biological resources and energy. Circularity through IS solutions can boost the value generated of biological resources, maintaining this value for longer in the biological economy by the implementation of the use of sustainable biomass. (European Commission, 2024). There are some examples of bio-based IS methodologies as:

- **ELLIPSE³¹** (Efficient and Novel Waste Streams Co-processing to Obtain Bio-based Solutions for Packaging and Agricultural Sector): It is a EU funded project based on the management of slaughterhouses and paper and pulp sludge processes to obtain PHAs, benefiting both the packaging and agricultural sectors. Contributing to the preservation of resources and the minimization of the production of waste.
- **SYMRAFT³²** The goal of the project is to foster the repurposing of industrial waste into innovative craft products. It aims to close the gap between different industries and the craft sector.
- **Uplift³³** (sUustainable PLastics for the Food and drink packaging indusTRY): the concept of this project is to implement the biological depolymerization technology in the established recycling processes. The bio-depolymerization processes are a tool to improve the eco-design and development of renewable and recyclable polymers, enhancing the circular economy. The use of biological depolymerization into the current recycling process fosters the capability of managing large amounts of non-renewable plastics.

The majority of the IS solutions within this category have received European, national or local funding such as Life+, H2020, SPIRE and INTERREG. However, many of them have become inactive after the funding ended, not resulting in commercial models or active case studies in the long term.

²⁹ Redol. (2023, April 20)

³⁰ (ACR+), D. P. (n.d.)

³¹ CORDIS (2023b, June 26)

³² Interreg. (2024)

³³ CORDIS. (2024, February 27)

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2.4. BARRIERS AND CONSTRAINTS FOR IS SOLUTIONS

It is shown that IS solutions with potential to enhance environmental and economic benefits already work in Europe. However, the potential to scale up these interactions is difficult to carry out due to different barriers such as regulatory, technological, economic, financial, communicational and risk and responsibility barriers.

The main barriers to overcome by the IS solutions are in many cases:

- The **governmental support** is key to improve the IS solutions, which promotes symbiotic activity and integrates the IS solutions in the management leadership and practices. However, successful IS solutions development requires an enabling governmental aligned environmental approach that includes appropriate market stimulus and regulatory instruments . (Watkins et al., 2013)
- **Directives and regulations** are a barrier to the IS solution implementation due to absent or rigid current regulatory framework. Likewise, the industry needs to obtain approvals for reuse of waste streams by regulatory agencies and intermediaries, and this will hinder the potential exchanges of materials and energy. Thus, new regulations are needed to foster the IS solutions. (Singh et al., 2020)
- **Lack of technical knowledge** and information of materials, processes and by-product exchanges is a barrier in IS solutions. There is a lack of technical information about the industrial waste streams. There exists an objection to sharing this knowledge across industries (Raabe et al., 2017), such as the lack of technical expertise to identify new perspectives and potential synergies, lack of time and resources within the companies, costs associated with transport and storage of materials, etc. (European Commission, 2018c)
- The **required changes in current practices** usually block the IS solutions. It is necessary to create new business mindsets that overcome these barriers, considering IS solutions as a new approach to improve the business models, not as a problem. (Vladimirova et al., 2018)
- **Financial barriers** are a critical element for the implementation of IS solutions. The fact of pricing of waste resources can be a barrier. Often, the valorisation of waste in a new raw material cannot be economically done. The potential hazardous elements in waste can be a big economic risk (Salmi et al., 2011). The current waste market is not sufficiently consolidated, and there is a lack of demand and supply waste recovery, the waste stream is not commonly used as a resource. (Boom-Cárcamo et al., 2022)
- **Informational barriers** are the gap which exists when interested people do not have access to key information at the correct moment. If there is poor information, it is difficult to know new uses for the waste streams. (Chertow et al., 2007) Founding a communication platform is crucial for EIP projects, considering that one of the big barriers faced by industries in IS solutions is the lack of information about available and possible by-products. Hence, a collaboration platform can be helpful for businesses engaging in a symbiotic relationship. (Raabe et al., 2017).
- **Cultural and cognitive barriers** are one of the most important barriers for the development of IS solutions. It is pointed out that waste is usually perceived as

something negative by companies. This makes businesses unwilling to focus on waste and collaborating in IS solutions. It is difficult for businesses to integrate waste into their processes due to waste usually being ignored. (Notarnicola et al., 2016).

Another fundamental issue that can act as a barrier to IS solutions is the match of the **timing** in which a waste is generated and when it may be needed. The most significant barriers could be the risk and the uncertainty linked to IS solutions. (European Commission, 2018)

The companies are used to working in the traditional competitive way and thus it is quite difficult to further create synergies. Normally, they do not trust to share information to each other, this perpetuates the linear value chains. The fact of turning waste in a resource is currently possible but companies are often distrustful. The firms do not want to take the risk of a systemic potential failure which is a cascading danger of an IS solution. Furthermore, the possible risk of hazardous waste leakage and the possible expense of adopting the IS solutions are perceived as a barrier to implementation of the IS solutions due to the strict legal frameworks involved. (Scaler, 2020a)

3. CONCLUSIONS

IS solutions across Europe vary in terms of scope and scale. However, there are certain trends among them. On one hand, IS solutions in the north of Europe tend to be self-organised, local for a specific area and with both public funding from local administrations and private. Thus, self-organised networks have been established in the Scandinavian countries since the end of World War II. This is mainly found in the northern part of Norway, Sweden and Finland, where resources are scarce, and industries tend to be located close together. In addition, the high restrictions regarding waste management and resource use promote the creation of synergies. These self-organised IS solutions have been classified as approaches, habitually called EIP, and implementing energy exchanges and waste streams as new resources. The approaches on the bio-based sector are key to foster the transformation of the bio-industry towards zero waste in accordance with the European Green Deal. The use of bio-based products from wastewater, agri-food, industrial crops, or food waste is the way to avoid the perpetuation of the linear consumption of resources, mainly non-renewable resources. The bio-based IS approaches foster this transformation towards zero emission and sustainable economy.

On the other hand, some IS solutions are associated with specific governmental or European funding, which allows them to operate while the fundings are active, but they tend to become inactive some years after finishing the funding.

Hence, there are certain characteristics that have been found in common in the more successful, long-lasting solutions and that is:

- Facilitate exchange between involved stakeholders from different sectors. It can be achieved through workshops, questionnaires, waste audits, etc. Furthermore, it is essential to have contact.
- Provide technical support to spot potential synergies between industries from different sectors and to overcome the legislation barriers from each country.
- Unify recollection of data regarding implemented or potential synergies.

Digital platforms usually are initiatives being part of an EU funded project, and tend to have a short life, as they only establish simple synergies and do not allow more complex networks or analysis. This happens to most platforms that do not have technical support from experts. Local and regional platforms are the most common platforms that connect different businesses in the same area, helping to foster synergies and exchanges of waste and energy. National platforms, supported by European funding and national agencies, promote the IS solutions on a national scale. They focus on creating a network of stakeholders, establishing new sustainable relationships and improving materials and knowledge synergies, leading to a circular economy. Finally, the international platforms are based on the same concept as previous platforms, with a holistic approach, implementing innovative solutions such as sharing resources, energy and waste. Commonly, the platforms are not specifically oriented towards bio-based industry, however, the bio-based IS solutions and sharing of biowaste and bioresources are a main part of their scope.

Methodologies, such as NISP, tend to establish more complex networks and have a team of experts to engage with stakeholders and help establish synergies, which elongates the lifespan of the projects. Within these, bio-based methodologies are a clear example of the necessity to find solutions to achieve a closed-loop bio-economy. They are focused on resource efficiency, boosting the exchange of different bio-based waste streams between stakeholders, minimising the production of waste, and using the innovation as a powerful tool to improve new materials and processes starting from the biowaste, which would otherwise end up in a landfill.

Assessing the performance of the IS solutions is difficult because of the gap of balanced frameworks to analyse and a big lack of good quality data reported by stakeholders. The IS solutions usually take a long time from initial phase to their development, which might discourage companies that use short reaction periods, among other barriers such as technological, governmental, financial or cultural barriers.

However, there are a multitude of implemented projects, case studies and tools that demonstrate how crucial fostering IS is to achieve a more sustainable future. Furthermore, this deliverable showcases many successful IS projects and its common qualities, which can be used as a roadmap to achieve a more unified IS network throughout Europe (European Commission, 2018).

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ANNEX 1

Platforms

IS solutions	Type of project	EU/ National / Local level	Country	Date	Target Sector / Area	Reference
BeCircle	N.A.	National	EU	n.d.	Resource efficiency	Climate-KIC (n.d.)
Ecoindustria	N.A.	Local	Spain	n.d.	Resource efficiency	Ecoindustria (2018c)
EPOS toolbox: Enhanced energy and resource Efficiency and Performance in process industry Operations via onsite and cross-sectorial Symbiosis	H2020-SPIRE Project	EU	EU	n.d.	Resource efficiency	EPOS (n.d.)
eSymbiosis - Development of knowledge-based web services to promote and advance Industrial Symbiosis in Europe	LIFE	National	Greece	2010-2014	Resource efficiency	LIFE 3.0 - LIFE Project Public Page. (n.d.)
Flow2	N.A.	National	Netherlands	2012	Waste/ Resource efficiency	FLOOW2 (n.d.)
InduSym. samen circular	N.A.	National	Netherlands	n.d.	Resource efficiency	Stichting Indusym - Homepage Indusym. (n.d.)

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MAESTRI: Energy and resource management systems for improved efficiency in the process of industries	H2020/ SPIRE Project	EU	Portugal , Italy, Germany, UK and Poland	2015-2019	Resource efficiency	CORDIS. (2022c, August 18)
Metropolitan area industrial symbiosis programme providing tools for municipalities and businesses	N.A.	Local	Spain	2020	Resource efficiency	Metròpolis Barcelona. Agència de Desenvolupament Econòmic. (n.d.)
SEEITS	N.A.	National	France	n.d.	Resource efficiency	SEITISS. (n.d.)
Sharebox	Horizon2020/ SPIRE	EU	EU	2020	Waste/ Resource efficiency	SHAREBOX – seamless sharing. (n.d.)
SIMBYLAY	FEDER	Local	Valencia , Spain	2018-2019	Resource efficiency	SIMBYLAY. (n.d.)
SIMVAL	Cofounded by Erasmus+	Local	Valencia , Spain	2018-2019	Resource efficiency	KATCH-e. (n.d.)
Siner. An online data management tool to implement industrial symbiosis projects towards a circular economy	H2020	National	Spain	n.d.	waste/ resource efficiency	CORDIS. (2022c, August 16)
Sustainable	H2020	EU	Greece,	2022-	Resource	B-WaterSmart.

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Knowledge-Portal on Water-Smartness and Circular Economy (CE) solutions. Part of the Water Europe project			Spain, Denmark and Austria	2026	efficiency	(2022)
Symbiosis Platform / (ICESP) Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	Interreg Europe	National	Italy	2020	Resource efficiency	ENEA, International Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development. (2015)
The Cambridge Value Mapping Tool	N.A.	National	UK	2015	Resource efficiency	University of Cambridge & Institute for Manufacturing (IfM) (n.d.)
Ultimate: Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis	H2020	National	Netherlands	2020	Water/ agri-food/ bio-based	ULTIMATE Water. (n.d.)
UNIDO: EIP Assessment Tool	UNIDO (United Nations Industrial Development Organization)	Global	Global	n.d.	Resource efficiency	UNIDO Knowledge Hub. Eco-Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)
Unido: EIP Opportunities Monitoring Tool	UNIDO (United Nations Industrial Development Organization)	Global	Global	n.d.	Resource efficiency	UNIDO Knowledge Hub. Eco-Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)
UNIDO: EIP Policy Support Tool	UNIDO (United	Global	Global	n.d.	Resource efficiency	UNIDO Knowledge Hub. Eco-

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	Nations Industrial Development Organization)					Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)
UNIDO: EIP Selection Tool	UNIDO (United Nations Industrial Development Organization)	Global	Global	n.d.	Resource efficiency	UNIDO Knowledge Hub. Eco-Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)
UNIDO: Industrial Symbiosis Identification Tool	UNIDO (United Nations Industrial Development Organization)	Global	Global	n.d.	Resource efficiency	UNIDO Knowledge Hub. Eco-Industrial Parks - Tools (n.d.)

ANNEX 2

Approaches

IS solutions	Type of project	EU/ National / Local level	Country	Date	Target Sector / Area	Reference
AgriMAX: Agri and food waste valorisation co-ops based on flexible multi-feedstocks biorefinery processing technologies for new high added value applications	H2020	EU	Belgium, Italy, Norway, Germany, Ireland, Austria, UK, Slovenia, Hungary, Netherlands & Spain	2016-2021	Resource efficiency/ agri-food/ bio-based	CORDIS. (2023b, June 28)
BASAJAUN: Building A SustainAble Joint between rurAl and UrbaN Areas Through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains	H2020	EU	Belgium, Italy, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands, Spain, Finland, France, Sweden, Portugal, Poland and Chile	2019-2024	Resource efficiency/ agri-food/ bio-based	CORDIS. (2024b, February 27)
Circular economy in Romania; An industrial synergy in the agri-food sector	N.A	National	Romania	2011	Agri-food / Waste/ bio-based	Frone, D. F., & Frone, S. (2007)
CO ₂ utilisation in the perspective of industrial ecology, an overview; F.D. Meylan	N.A.	Local	Various countries	n.d.	Resource efficiency	Meylan, F. D., Moreau, V., & Erkman, S. (2015)

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PlastiCircle: Improvement of the plastic packaging waste chain from a circular economy approach	H2020	EU	Alba Iulia (Romania), Valencia (Spain) and Utrecht (Netherlands)	2018	Resource efficiency	CORDIS. (2023a, March 10)
Industrial symbiosis networks and the contribution to environmental innovation: The case of the Landskrona industrial symbiosis programme	N.A.	Local	Landskrona, Sweden	2004	Agri-food/ waste / resource efficiency	Mirata, M., & Emtairah, T. (2005)
Port of Rotterdam	N.A.	Local	Rotterdam, Netherlands	n.d.	Energy / waste / resource efficiency	Baas, (2011)
Production synergies in the current biofuel industry: opportunities for development; Michael Martin	N.A.	Local	Sweden	n.d.	Resource efficiency	Martin, M., Svensson, N., Eklund, M., & Fonseca, J. (2012)
SYMBI: Industrial symbiosis for Regional Sustainable Growth and a Resource Efficient Circular Economy	Interreg	EU	Spain, Poland, Italy, Slovenia, Greece, Hungary and Finland	2016-2021	Water/ waste	Interreg Europe. (2016)
Systemic Analysis of the Contributions of Co-Located Industrial Symbiosis to Achieve Sustainable Development in an Industrial Park in	N.A.	National	Spain	n.d.	Energy/ water/ waste	Ruiz-Puente, C., & Jato-Espino, D. (2020)

Northern Spain						
Thams Klyngen and Naeringsagen i Orkdalsregionen	N.A.	National	Orkanger, Norway	2018	Resource efficiency / waste	Johnsen, I., Berlina, A., Lindberg, G., & Teräs, J. (2015)
Towards a Resilient and Resource-Efficient Local Food System Based on Industrial Symbiosis in Härnösand: A Swedish Case Study	N.A.	Local	Härnösand, Sweden	2022	Agri-food	Haller, H., Fagerholm, A.-S., Carlsson, P., Skoglund, W., van den Brink, P., Danielski, I., Brink, K., Mirata, M., & Englund, O. (2022)
Ultimate: Case Study 1. Tarragona. Increasing the capacity to recover water at an industrial complex	H2020	National	Tarragona, Spain	n.d.	Plastic and packaging	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Case Study 2. Water reuse and heat recovery for horticulture	H2020	National	Nieu Prinseland, Netherlands	2021-Onwards	Waste	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Case Study 3. Rosignano. Water reuse and material recovery in the chemical industry	H2020	National	Rosignano, Italy	2021-Onwards	Resource efficiency	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Case Study 4: Nafplio. Mobile wastewater treatment unit	H2020	National	Nafplio, Greece	2021-Onwards	Resource efficiency	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Case Study 5: Lleida, Ostrava. Water recycling in the beverage industry	H2020	National	Lleida, Spain and Ostrava, Czech Republic	2021-Onwards	Resource efficiency	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)

Ultimate: Case Study 6: Karmiel and Shafdan	H2020	National	Israel	2021-Onwards	Resource efficiency	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Case Study 8: Saint-Maurice l'Exil. Heat and Resource recovery in chemical incineration plant	H2020	National	Saint-Maurice de l'Exil, France	2021-Onwards	Resource efficiency	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Ultimate: Water Smart Industrial Symbiosis	H2020	National	Netherlands	2020	Water	ULTIMATE Water (n.d.)
Case study of a small-scale pyrolysis–biochar based system integrated in an olive farm in symbiosis with an olive mill	H2020	Local	Mediterranean region	N.A.	Resource efficiency	CORDIS. (2022c, August 16)
ECOMARK Project	Project	Local	Spain, Italy, France and Greece	2007-2013	Agri-food / waste/ bio-based	CORDIS. (2011, August 29)

As mentioned in the deliverable, EIP are the most typical approaches. The following table highlights all of the found EIP in Europe:

IS solutions	EU / National / Local level	Country	Target Sector / Area	Reference
Amaro Industrial Park	Local	Italy	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Basf Verbund site Ludwigshafen	Local	Germany	Water/ energy/ waste/resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014

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Bayer Industrial Park Brunsbüttel	Local	Germany	Water/waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Biopark Terneuzen	Local	Netherlands	Energy/waste/ bio-based/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Boruta Zgierz Industrial Park	Local	Poland	Energy/ waste/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Cairo Montenotte Industrial Park	Local	Italy	Waste	Massard et al., 2014
Camp CO2-Zero	Local	Germany	Energy	Massard et al., 2014
Chemical Industrial Park Knapsack	Local	Germany	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Chemical Valley Industrial Area	Local	France	Resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Chemie-und Industriepark Zeitz	Local	Germany	Water/waste/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Chemiepark Bitterfeld Wolfen	Local	Germany	Water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Chemiepark Delfzijl	Local	Netherlands	Energy/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Chempark Dormagen	Local	Germany	Resource efficiency/ water/waste/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Chempark Krefeld Uerdingen	Local	Germany	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014

Chempark Leverkusen	Local	Germany	waste/water	Massard et al., 2014
Cicle	Local	Spain	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Créalys® Scientific Park	Local	Belgium	Energy/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Croix-Fort Artisanal Park	Local	France	Resource efficiency/ water/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Deux Synthe Industrial Park	Local	France	Resource efficiency/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Dow Valuepark	Local	Germany	Resource efficiency/ water/waste	Massard et al., 2014C
Ecolys® Park	Local	Belgium	Energy/ waste/ water/ bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
Ecopark Hartberg	Local	Austria	water/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Ecopark Windhof	Local	Luxemburg	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Eko-park d.o.o Lendava	Local	Slovenia	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Emmtec Industry & Business Park	Local	Netherlands	Resource efficiency/ water/waste/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Envipark (Parco Scientifico Tecnologico per l'Ambiente)	Local	Italy	Energy/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Felsenpark	Local	Germany	Resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Galaxia Industrial Park	Local	Belgium	Resource efficiency/ waste	Massard et al., 2014

Gersthofen Industriepark	Local	Germany	Bio-based/ water/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Gewerbenetzwerk Pfaffengrund	Local	Germany	Energy/ waste/resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Grand Troyes Park	Local	France	Resource efficiency/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Händelö Island	Local	Sweden	Agri-food/ bio-based/ waste/energy	Massard et al., 2014
Harjavalta Industrial Eco-Park	Local	Finland	Energy/water/waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Havre Industrial-Harbour Park	Local	France	Energy/waste/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Honeywell Seelze	Local	Germany	Energy/waste/water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Industriepark Höchst	Local	Germany	Water/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Industriepark Kalle Albert	Local	Germany	Energy/ water	Massard et al., 2014
InfraLeuna	Local	Germany	Energy/waste/water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Jämtland County	Local	Sweden	Resource efficiency/ energy/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Kaiserbaracke Industrial Park	Local	Belgium	Resource efficiency/ based bio-	Massard et al., 2014
Kalundborg network	Local	Denmark	Energy/water/waste	Massard et al., 2014
Kemi-Tornio Industrial	Local	Sweden	Waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014

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Symbiosis network				
Kymi Eco-Industrial Park	Local	Finland	bio-based/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Lagny-sur-Marne and La Courtilière Industrial Parks	Local	France	Resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Landskrona Industrial Symbiosis	Local	Sweden	Energy/ waste/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Les Sohettes Bio-refinery	Local	France	Bio-based/ water/ waste/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Lucento Industrial Area	Local	Italy	waste	Massard et al., 2014
MABU (Material Business) Project	Local	Finland	Waste/ resource efficiency/ bio- based	Massard et al., 2014
Malmö Cleantech City	Local	Sweden	Waste/ water/ bio-based/ resource efficiency/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Marl Chemical Park	Local	Germany	Energy/waste/w ater/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Moerdijk	Local	Netherlands	Resource efficiency/waste/ energy	Massard et al., 2014
Monteras	Local	Sweden	Energy/ waste/ bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
Navicelli di Pisa Park	Local	Italy	Energy	Massard et al., 2014

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Nogent Industrial Basin	Local	France	Bio-based/ agri-food/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Norrköping and Linköping	Local	Sweden	Resource efficiency/ energy/ bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
Oberbruch Industry Park	Local	Germany	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Padova Industrial Park	Local	Italy	Energy/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Parc de l'Alba	Local	Spain	Energy/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Parque Tecnológico Galicia Tecnópole	Local	Spain	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Parque tecnológico y logístico de Vigo	Local	Spain	waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Pharma und Chemiapark Wuppertal	Local	Germany	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Plaine de l'Ain Industrial Park	Local	France	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Police Industrial Park	Local	Poland	Waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Polígono As Gándaras	Local	Spain	waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Polígono industrial de Alfacar	Local	Spain	Energy/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014

Polígono Industrial El Congost	Local	Spain	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Polígono O Ceao	Local	Spain	waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Ponte Rizzoli Industrial Park	Local	Italy	Energy/ waste/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Prato 1st Industrial Macrolotto	Local	Italy	Energy/ water	Massard et al., 2014
Pulawy Production Park	Local	Poland	Water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Rantasalmi Eco-industrial Park	Local	Finland	Energy/waste/bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
Relvão Eco-Industrial Park	Local	Portugal	Waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
ResiSt Project. Is part of the UNEP Urban Resilience program	Local	Portugal	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Rietvelden - De Vutter	Local	Netherlands	Energy/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Roche en Brènil Wood Ecopole	Local	France	Waste/ bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
San Daniele s.c.a.r.l Agrifood Park	Local	Italy	Agri-food/ bio-based/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Santa Perpètua de Mogoda industrial area	Local	Spain	Energy/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Schwedt Industrial Park	Local	Germany	Water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014

Södra Cell - Mönsterås Network	Local	Sweden	Energy/ waste/ agri-food/ bio- based	Massard et al., 2014
South Groningen Business Park	Local	Netherlands	Energy/ water/ bio-based	Massard et al., 2014
Styria Network	Local	Austria	Waste/ water/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Technopôle Savoie Technolac	Local	France	Resource efficiency/ waste	Massard et al., 2014
Tenneville Industrial Park	Local	Belgium	Water	Massard et al., 2014
Torvilliers Industrial Park	Local	France	Waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Uimaharju Industrial Area	Local	Finland	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Zero Emission Park Bottrop	Local	Germany	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Zero Emission Park Bremen	Local	Germany	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014
Zero Emission Park Kaiserslautern	Local	Germany	Energy/ water/ waste/ resource efficiency	Massard et al., 2014

ANNEX 3

Methodologies

IS solutions	Type of project	EU/ National / Local level	Involved countries	Date	Target Sector / Area	Reference
Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	Interreg	EU	Finland, Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Poland, Russia	2014-2020	Waste	Project - Baltic industrial symbiosis. (n.d.)
BeonNAT: Innovative value chains from tree & shrub species grown in marginal lands as a source of biomass for bio-based industries	H2020	EU	Spain, Italy, Germany, Romania, Portugal and UK	2020-2025	Bio-based	CORDIS (2024b, July 30)
CIRC-PACK: Towards Circular Economy in the Plastic Packaging Value Chain	H2020	EU	Spain, Italy, Netherlands, Croatia, Turkey, UK, Germany and France	2017-2020	Plastic and packaging/ bio-based	CORDIS (2023c, July 11).
CircLean	Interreg	Local	Slovenia, Hungary, Spain, UK, etc.	2019-2022	Resource efficiency	Cir©Lean. (n.d.)
CIRCULAR BIOCARBON: Turning carbon of complex organic urban waste streams into value-added products	H2020	EU	Spain, Italy, France and Germany	2021-2026	Waste/ bio-based	Circular Biocarbon. (n.d.)
CORALIS: Creation of new value chain Relations through novel Approaches facilitating	H2020	EU	Spain, Sweden, Italy,	2020-2024	Resource efficiency	CORALIS. (2020, April 27)

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Long-term Industrial Symbiosis			Austria, Greece, Turkey and Belgium			
ECOREG	LIFE	National	Romania	2009-2011	Waste	European Commission. LIFE. (2009)
ELIPSE: Efficient and Novel Waste Streams Co-processing to Obtain Bio-based Solutions for Packaging and Agricultural Sector	HE	EU	Countries involved: Sweden, Germany, Italy, Switzerland, France, Netherlands, Belgium, Greece and Hungary	2023-2027	Waste/ bio-based	CORDIS (2023b, June 26)
FIIS: Finish Industrial Symbiosis	Interreg	National	Finland	2013-ongoing	Resource efficiency	Interreg Europe - Sharing solutions for better policy. (n.d.)
FISSAC: Fostering industrial symbiosis for a sustainable resource intensive industry across the extended construction value chain	H2020	EU	Belgium, Spain, Italy, UK, Hungary, Czech Republic, Turkey, Sweden and Germany	2015-2020	Waste/ resource efficiency	ACR+ (n.d.)
H4C ECoP: Hubs for Circularity European Community of Practice	EU-Funded	EU	Germany	2022-2026	Resource efficiency	ICLEI europe •• projects. (n.d.)
ISIM-TCC Industrial Symbiosis	LIFE	National	Hungary	2010-	Resource	European

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as an Innovative Method in Tackling Climate Change				2012	efficiency	Commision. LIFE public database. (2010)
ISS: Industrial Symbiosis Service	N.A.	National	Ireland	2007-ongoing	Resource efficiency	Invest Northern Ireland. (n.d.)
KARMA2020: Industrial Feather Waste Valorisation for Sustainable KeRatin based MAterials	H2020	EU	Spain, Finland, Sweden, Belgium, Poland, France, Netherlands, Germany, Italy and Israel	2017-2019	Plastic and packaging/waste/textile/ bio-based	CORDIS (2023c, September 11)
NISP: National Industrial Symbiosis Programme UK	N.A.	National	UK		Resource efficiency	International Synergies. (n.d.)
PNSI: National Industrial Symbiosis Programme	National Inter-company synergies	National	France	2015-2017	Resource efficiency	Institut National de l'Économie Circulaire. (2017)
REDOL: Aragon's REgional Hub for circularity: Demonstration of Local industrial-urban symbiosis initiatives	HE	EU	Case study based in: Spain	2022-2026	Waste/water	Redol. (2023, April 20)
SCALER: Scaling European Resources with Industrial Symbiosis	H2020	EU	Portugal, UK, France, Swizerland and Germany	2017-2020	Resource efficiency/waste	Scaler. (2020a)
SPIRE-SAIS: Skills Alliance for Industrial Symbiosis- a Cross-	Funded by	EU	Various	2020-2024	Resource efficiency	IMA Europe. (n.d.)

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sectoral Blueprint for a Sustainable Process Industry	Erasmus + Programme of the European Union					
SYMCRAFT	Interreg	EU	Italy, Czech republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, Slovenia, Austria, Germany	2024-2026	Resource efficiency/ bio-based/ agri-food/ waste	Interreg. (2024)
SYMITES: Industrial Urban Symbiosis and its social, economic and environmental impact on different European regions	HE	EU	Spain, Belgium, Austria, Greece, Italy, Germany, Denmark, Israel and Romania	2022-2026	Water/ waste/ bio-based	CORDIS (2022, July 28)
SymNet Industrial Symbiosis Network for Environment Protection and Sustainable Development in Black Sea Basin	Interreg	EU	Bulgaria, Romania, Moldavia, Turkey	2011-2013	Resource efficiency	Interreg. (2012)
TRIS: Transition Regions towards Industrial Symbiosis	Interreg	EU	Various countries	2016-2021	Waste	TRIS. (n.d.)
UBIS - Urban Baltic Industrial Symbiosis	Interreg	National	Sweden, Lithuania, Denmark, Germany and Poland	2017-2019	Resource efficiency	Interreg. South Baltic. (2017)

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Uplift: sUustainable PLastics for the Food and drink packaging industry	H2020	EU	Denmark, Germany, Austria, Sweden, Croatia, Belgium, Spain and Ireland	2021-2025	Plastic and packaging	CORDIS (2024, February 27)
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